

Simplification Strategies in Medical Texts Tıbbi Metinlerde Basitleştirme Yöntemleri

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Abstract

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Medical translation can be a critical factor in providing health care to foreigners or minorities. To maintain accurate translation of medical texts, translators use some translation strategies. One of the most common of these strategies is the "translation universals" proposed by Baker. The concept of translation universals is an important area of interest in the field of translation studies. The essence of the research consists of two research questions: "What is the distribution of lexical simplification strategies in the summaries of medical texts translated from Turkish to English?", "What is the distribution of syntactic simplification strategies in the summaries of medical texts translated from Turkish to English?". In this context, the aim of the study is to explain how the simplification strategy is preserved in the summaries of Turkish master's theses in the field of medicine and their English translations. To study simplification, three basic simplification taxonomies have been applied. The main taxonomy is Honeyfield's linguistic simplification, other taxonomies are Blum-Kulka and Levenston's lexical simplification and Mountford's syntactic simplification. According to the findings, lexical simplification is used in medical texts rather than syntactic simplification. It is expected that this study will raise awareness of translation studies in the field of medicine and provide insight to translators and all medical professionals about the medical translation techniques that will be used in the future.

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Öz

Tıbbi çeviri, yabancılara veya azınlıklara sağlık hizmeti sunulmasında kritik bir faktör olabilmektedir. Tıbbi metinlerin çevirisini doğru bir şekilde sürdürmek için çevirmenler bazı çeviri stratejilerinden yararlanırlar. Bu stratejilerden en yaygın olanlarından biri Baker tarafından önerilen "çeviri evrenselleri"dir. Çeviri evrenselleri kavramı, çeviribilim alanında önemli bir ilgi alanıdır. Araştırmanın özünü iki araştırma sorusu oluşturmaktadır: "Türkçeden İngilizceye çevrilen tıp metinlerinin özetlerinde sözcük sadeleştirme stratejilerinin dağılımı nasıldır?", "Türkçeden İngilizceye çevrilen tıp metinlerinin özetlerinde sözdizimsel sadeleştirme stratejilerinin dağılımı nasıldır?". Bu bağlamda çalışmanın amacı, tıp alanındaki Türkçe yüksek lisans tezlerinin özetlerinde ve bunların İngilizce tercümelelerinde sadeleştirme stratejisinin nasıl korunduğunun açıklanmasıdır. Sadeleştirmeyi incelemek için, temel olarak üç basitleştirme taksonomisi uygulanmıştır. Ana taksonomi Honeyfield'in dilbilimsel basitleştirmesidir, diğer taksonomiler Blum-Kulka ve Levenston'ın sözcüksel basitleştirmesi ve Mountford'un sözdizimsel basitleştirmesidir. Elde edilen bulgulara göre tıp metinlerinde sözdizimsel sadeleştirmeden çok sözcüksel sadeleştirme kullanılmaktadır. Bu çalışmanın tıp alanında yapılan tercüme çalışmalarına bir farkındalık kazandırarak bundan sonra kullanılacak tıbbi tercüme teknikleri hakkında tercümanlara ve tüm tıp çalışanlarına bir içgörü kazandırması beklenmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Tıbbi Çeviri, Çeviri Stratejiler,; Tercümede Sadeleştirme, Sözdizimsel Basitleştirme, Evrensel Çeviri.

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Introduction

The importance of the field of medicine, whose history dates back to ancient times, cannot be ignored. As this field progressed, texts related to the area of medicine began to appear more, and the developments in the field showed the need to transfer these developments to other cultures and societies, resulting in the translation of medical texts. Based on this, it is possible to say that translation is a crucial factor in disseminating knowledge and discoveries in the medical field. Medical translation concerns several subject areas, including pharmacology, medical rescue system, surgery, obstetrics, paediatrics, psychiatry, internal medicine, oncology, cardiology, and other fields. Thus, medical translation can be critical in providing healthcare services to foreigners or minorities. (Karwacka, 2015). However, when translating medical texts, translators may face some difficulties as the medical field has its own unique terminology. For this reason, it is essential to provide lexical equivalence and to transfer the language correctly.

Translators utilize some translation strategies to maintain the translation of medical texts properly. One of the most common strategies is "Translation Universals," proposed by Baker (1993). According to Baker, universals of translation are linguistic features that typically occur in translated rather than original texts and are thought to be independent of the influence of the specific language pairs involved in translation. Translation universals include normalization, explicitation, and simplification. Normalization is "the tendency to conform to patterns and practices typical of the target language, even exaggerating them" (Baker, 2019, p. 45). Explicitation is the tendency to "spell things out rather than leave them implicit" (Baker, 2019, p.49). Features of "explicitation" are all those grammatical and lexical elements that are absent in the source text and that render the target text more precise and unambiguous. As a definition, simplification is "the tendency to simplify the language used in translation" (Baker, 2019, p. 49).

Literature Review

A large and growing body of literature has compared translations with their corresponding source texts regarding the deployment of translation universals. Xiao (2010) explored potential features of translational Chinese based on two balanced monolingual comparable corpora of translated and native Mandarin Chinese. The implications of the study for translation universals hypotheses were also discussed. Rabadan et al. (2009) surveyed to identify low-quality rendering of grammatical features when translating from English into Spanish using translation universals. The study aims to demonstrate the usefulness of a corpus-based contrastive methodology. Ippolito's (2014) book tests whether simplification, normalization, and explicitation processes dominate children's literature in Italy. It was hypothesized that a different translation context implies other translation processes. Goh et al. (2016) argue that translated English texts hold particular linguistic properties distinctive from non-translated English texts on a substantial level. Certain translational instances were examined by compiling the purpose-end comparable corpora of translated and non-translated English abstracts of theses and dissertations written by Korean and American graduates. The results indicated that various translational shifts were salient even though some predictors were not sufficiently feasible to verify the universal features of the translated English texts.

Translation universals are a significant area of interest within translation studies. Up to now, far too little attention has been paid to the employment of translation universals in medical texts (Ilisei et al., 2009). The specific objective of the study is to explain how the simplification strategy was maintained in the abstracts of Masters Theses in Turkish and their English translation. It is assumed that this study provides insights into the employment of the simplification strategy in translating medical texts. Because by using the simplification universal, texts become more understandable to the reader. A text is simplified to make it easier to understand texts that contain terms, especially in medicine, with its own terminology.

The present study examines the simplification strategies in medical texts translated from Turkish to English. It specifically concentrated on the abstracts of the medical texts.

The following research question constitutes the essence of the study;

- What is the distribution of lexical simplification strategies in the abstracts of medical texts translated from Turkish to English?
- What is the distribution of syntactic simplification strategies in the abstracts of medical texts translated from Turkish to English?

Methodology

Data Collection

This study aims to investigate the simplification strategies in the abstracts of MA theses translated from Turkish to English in medicine. These texts comprise MA theses written by Turkish speakers of English in medicine as they were shorter than PhD theses and easier to read. They were chosen randomly between 2020 and 2023 as the Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education did not include the pdf versions of various theses written before 2020. They were open sources available at the Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education. To ensure the validity of the data, 10 MA theses were chosen from each year. A total of 40 abstracts in the field of medicine constituted the data of the present study. Since the present study aims to examine the simplification strategies in the medical texts translated from Turkish to English, the data was subdivided into two categories: the abstracts written in Turkish and their translation to English. The data coding in this paper was arranged as the year of publication and the first initial of the language, and thematic analysis was used. To illustrate, 2020-T-1 represented the first abstract in Turkish written in 2020, and 2020-E-1 was its translation to English.

Data Analysis

To examine the simplification, three taxonomies of simplification were applied. Honeyfield (1977) proposes two categories of simplification. *Lexical* and *syntactic* simplification. *Lexical* simplification is one of the sub-categories of linguistic simplification, and it proposes simplifying a text using fewer different words. *Syntactic* simplification is the other sub-category of linguistic simplification. It offers to avoid creating semantic gaps, such as splitting long and complex sentences, avoiding complex tense structures, and using models with their precise meanings.

In the present study, the simplification examples found in the data were first categorized as *lexical* and *syntactic*. Another taxonomy suggested by Blum-Kulka and Levenston (1978, p. 399) was used to classify the lexical simplification strategies in the data. They define *lexical* simplification as “the process and result of making do with fewer words” and propose six sub-categories of this simplification type:

- Superordinate terms: The use of superordinate terms in the target language with an additional explanation to convey an exact meaning when a semantic gap is encountered in the text.
- Approximation: The use of less complex terms
- Synonymy: This means using different words with the same meaning instead of terms in professional or academic jargon.
- Transfer: The use of terms related to the target culture instead of cultural elements
- Circumlocution: The use of more words than necessary.
- The analysis of *syntactical/structural* simplification is based on the five methods presented by Mountford (1976, p. 432):
- Long embedded sentences divide long sentences containing gerunds or conjunctions.
- Nominalisation separates the sentence by converting nouns or noun phrases into verbs.
- Tense relationships are the standardization of tenses in sentences.
- Modals can be described as using verb modals by explaining them.
- Anaphoric links can be defined as using personal names instead of pronouns.

The simplification examples found in the data were first categorized as lexical and syntactic in the present study. The second step of the analysis was to find the distribution of the sub-categories of the *lexical* simplification suggested by Blum-Kulka and Levenston (1978). The third step of the analysis was to observe the examples and the distribution of the syntactic simplification in the data. The distribution of all the categories and sub-categories was displayed in tables with their frequencies and percentages. Examples from the data for each category were also given to clarify the strategies' employment.

Findings and Discussion

The abstracts of 40 MA theses written by Turkish speakers of English in medicine and their translations were examined for the research. *Lexical* simplification, suggested by Blum-Kulka and Levenston (1978), and *syntactical/structural* simplification, suggested by Mountford (1976), were taken as the basis for the analysis.

Table 1 displays the overall distribution of *lexical* and *syntactic* simplification strategies in the abstracts of Turkish MA theses and their English translations. One thousand one hundred twelve *lexical* simplification examples were found in the data with a percentage of 96.27%. *Syntactic* simplification strategies constituted 3.73% of the simplification strategy in our data. They had 43 frequency counts.

Table 1.

The overall distribution of lexical and syntactic simplification in the data

	N	%
<i>Lexical</i>	1112	96.27
<i>Syntactic</i>	43	3.73

Having a general picture of the simplification strategy after Table 1, Table 2 shows the *lexical* simplification strategies observed in the present study.

Table 2 displays the distribution of sub-categories of *lexical* simplification strategies in the data. 1081 transfer examples were found in the data, with a percentage of 97.21%. Synonymy constituted 1.53% of the *lexical* simplification in our data. It had 17 frequency counts. Moreover, finally, 14 circumlocution examples were found in the data with a percentage of 1.26%.

Table 2.

The distribution of the sub-categories of lexical simplification

Lexical Simplification	N	%
Superordinate terms	0	0
Approximation	0	0
Synonymy	17	1.53
Transfer	1081	97.21
Circumlocution	14	1.26

Transfer

The transfer uses terms related to the target culture instead of cultural elements. 1081 examples were found in the data with a percentage of 97.21.

ST: Bu çalışmanın sonucunda elde edilen sonuçların bu alanlarda faydalı olacağını ve daha sonra yapılacak olan **altın oran** araştırmalarında ön çalışma niteliği taşıyacağını düşünmekteyiz.

TT: We believe that the results obtained in this study will be beneficial in these areas and set a precedent for future studies on the **golden ratio**.

In this example, the mathematical term "altın oran" in the source text was translated similarly into the target text and transferred.

ST: Böbrek gelişiminde **JAK/STAT** sinyal yolağı önemli bir rol oynamaktadır.

TT: Signaling via the **JAK/STAT** MAPK pathways is essential for the kidney's response to injury in disease.

In this example, the medical term "JAK/STAT" was translated word for word in the target text and transferred. Also, "MAPK," which is not in the source text, was used in the target text. This is the wrong translation.

Synonymy

As a simplification strategy, synonymy means using different words with the same meaning instead of terms in professional or academic jargon. 17 examples were found in the data with a percentage of 1.53.

Examples:

ST: Amaç: Tez çalışmasında **anaerobik** egzersizin koku duyusu üzerindeki etkilerinin araştırılması amaçlanmıştır.

TT: The study aimed to investigate the acute effects of **short-term** exercise on olfactory performance.

In this example, instead of using "anaerobik" in ST directly and transferring, the word "short-term" was used with the same meaning. This indicates that the synonymy was used. In addition, the term "acute," which is not in the source text, was used in the target text, and the "koku duyusu" in the ST was translated as "olfactory" and transferred.

ST: Müdahale grubuyla yapılan birinci yüz yüze görüşmede katılımcıların diyabet öyküsü alınmış, hasta katılımı kavramı açıklanarak **bireye özgü** bakım hedefleri belirlenmiş ve ev tabanlı alıştırmalar tanıtılmıştır.

TT: In the first session with the intervention group, participants' illness experience was collected, the concept of patient engagement was clarified, **specific** care goals were identified, and home-based exercises were introduced.

In this example, "bireye özgü" in the ST was translated as "specific" in the TT, giving us the synonymy. Also, "diyabet öyküsü" in the ST was translated as "illness experience" in the TT, which can be seen as synonymy. Finally, "yüz yüze" in the ST was omitted in the TT.

Circumlocution

Circumlocution is the use of more words than necessary. In the examples below, explanations were given to understand the terms in TT. More words were used in the target text than in the source text, indicating circumlocution. 14 examples were found in the data with a percentage of 1.26.

Examples:

ST: Sonuçlar MTT, TAK, TOD, Flow sitometri ve q-PCR testleri ile analiz edilmiştir.

TT: Results were analyzed by MTT, total antioxidant capacity (TAC), total oxidant status (TOS), Flow cytometry, and q-PCR tests.

ST: Bulgular: Sentezlenen quantum dotlar ile biyokonjuge nano yapıların gerçekleştirilen SEM, TEM, FTIR, XRD analizleri ile doğru bir biçimde sentezlendiği belirlenmiştir.

TT: Results: It was determined that bioconjugated nanostructures with synthesized quantum dots were synthesized correctly by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR), X-Ray Crystallography (XRD) analyzes.

Table 3 presents the distribution of sub-categories of *syntactic* simplification in the data. 21 modal examples were found in the data, with a percentage of 48.84. Long embedded sentences constituted

25.58% of the *syntactic* simplification in our data. It had 11 frequency counts. Moreover, finally, 11 anaphoric links examples were found in the data with a percentage of 25.58%.

Table 3.

The distribution of the sub-categories of syntactic simplification

<i>Syntactic Simplification</i>	N	%
Long embedded sentences	11	25.58
Nominalisations	0	0
Tense relationships	0	0
Modals	21	48.84
Anaphoric Links	11	25.58

Modals

As a simplification strategy, modals can be described as using verb modals by explaining them. Since modals are added to the end of verbs in Turkish and used as separate words in English, they are primarily seen in English. 21 examples were found in the data, with a percentage of 48.84.

Examples:

ST: Sonuç olarak hem torasik ESP bloğu yönetimi hem de i.v. lidokain infüzyon yöntemi torakotomi uygulanacak hastalarda etkili analjezik yöntem **olabileceğini**, postoperative dönemde ek analjezik ihtiyacını ve opioid tüketim miktarını azalttığını, bunlarla birlikte erken postoperatif dönemde istirahatte ve aktivitede VAS skorlarını tolere edilebilir düzeylere getirebildiğini gördük.

TT: As a result, we have seen that both thoracic ESP block and IV lidocaine infusion methods **can be** effective analgesic methods in patients undergoing thoracotomy, reduce the need for additional analgesics and the amount of opioid consumption in the postoperative period, and bring VAS scores at rest and activity to tolerable levels in the early postoperative period.

In this example, the verb 'olabilecek' should be stated with the 'may' modal, but instead, 'can be' was used in TT.

ST: Yüksek riskli hastalarda ameliyat sonrası KT **mutlaka uygulanmaktadır**.

TT: Post-operative chemotherapy **should be given** to high-risk patients.

In this example, the word 'mutlaka' should be translated as 'must,' but instead, 'should' was used in TT. This is the wrong translation.

Long Embedded Sentences

As a simplification strategy, long embedded sentences can be defined as the division of long sentences containing gerunds or conjunctions. In the examples below, a long sentence in ST was divided into two in TT. 11 examples were found in the data with a percentage of 25.58.

Examples:

ST: Ancak dönüştürücü büyüme faktörü-Beta (TGF-beta) değerinin kontrol grubuna göre glutamin grubunda daha düşük olduğu ve fibroblast büyüme faktörü 2 değerinin ise sham grubuna göre glutamin grubunda daha düşük olduğu görülmüştür.

TT: However, transforming growth factor-beta was significantly low in the glutamine group compared to the control group. Similarly, fibroblast growth factor 2 was significantly low in the glutamine group compared to the sham group.

In this example, since the source text has a long sentence connected by the conjunction "and," this sentence was split in two in the target text.

ST: BKİ, sigara kullanımı, beslenme eğitimi alma, sağlık çalışanı olma durumlarının yeme farkındalığı ve sağlıklı beslenmeye ilişkin tutum üzerine etkili bulunurken; cinsiyet faktörünün sadece yeme

farkındalığı üzerine etkili olduğu, fiziksel aktivitenin de sadece sağlıklı beslenmeye ilişkin tutum üzerine etkili olduğu bulunmuştur.

TT: While BMI, smoking, getting nutrition education, and being a health worker were effective on mindful eating and attitudes towards healthy nutrition. It was found that the gender factor was only influential on mindful eating, and physical activity was only effective on the attitude towards healthy nutrition.

In this example, the sentence was split into two in the target text since there is a long sentence connected with the verbal adverb “bulunurken” in the source text.

Anaphoric Links

Anaphoric links, as a simplification strategy, can be defined as using personal names instead of pronouns. In the examples below, instead of writing the word's meaning as in the source text, an anaphoric link was used in the target text by using the abbreviations of the terms. Eleven examples were found in the data with a percentage of 25.58.

Example:

ST: Solunum testi sonrası kontrol grubundaki katılımcılar 8 dakika boyunca pasif olarak dinlenmiştir.

TT: After the **PNIF** test, the participants in the control group rested passively for eight minutes.

ST: Bu sonuçlara göre, **Kişiselleştirilmiş Hasta Katılım Planı'nın** diyabet öz yönetim eğitimine ek bir yöntem olarak kullanılması ve polikliniklerde hasta takibine entegre edilmesi önerilmektedir.

TT: According to these results, it is recommended to combine **PHEinAction** with diabetes self-management education and integrate it into patient follow-up in outpatient clinics.

The present study was designed to explain how the simplification strategy was maintained in the abstracts of Masters Theses in Turkish and their English translation. As seen from the tables above, 6 types of simplification strategies were used in the texts. It can be seen from the data in Table 1 that the most commonly used simplification strategy in the translation of these abstracts was lexical simplification. As shown in Table 2, the results show that the most widely used lexical simplification technique in the translation of 40 MA theses abstracts was the “transfer,” with a rate of 97.21%.

One interesting finding is that the long embedded sentences (25.58%) and anaphoric links (25.58%) were used the least in the translations. Another finding is that syntactic simplification had a shallow rate (3.73%), although English and Turkish have different syntactic structures.

Discussion

It is no surprise that lexical simplification is the most used strategy when translating medical texts, as medical texts are complex pieces requiring word-basis changes to be intelligible. While the syntax of medical texts is quite like texts of other disciplines, the jargon is quite different and complex. As a result, word-basis changes are preferred over syntactic changes in the translation of medical texts so that the reader can understand the complex jargon and have an overall understanding of the text. As Baker (2019) argues, simplification necessarily means making things easier for the reader, namely understandable. However, it is also stated that simplification does not necessarily mean making things more explicit for the reader and breaking down the ambiguity of the text. Also, in Xiao's study (2010), it is stated that some find lexical simplification unpractical, thinking it makes the translation “patchy.” On the contrary, Blum and Levenston (1978) state that in some cases, lexical simplification is obligatory and works the best, especially in areas using complex terminology as the operating mechanism behind it is universal. Similarly, Kuusi (2006) suggested that simplification occurs as a tendency towards making things explicit, a characteristic of a natural translation process; namely, it is harmless and inevitable. In our case, it is pretty unusual for an average reader with an average educational background to fully understand a medical text with complex terms. Thus, in Turkish literature, if the translators' pursuit is to be read by the public and to make the public profit from the study, simplification is inevitable, at least to some extent. In this regard, for example, Rabadán et al. (2009) found out that, in a study conducted in a Spanish

context, translators tended to use the most frequently used, so-called “trendy” words both for the reader to become more interested in the text and for the text to be easily understood.

In fact, lexical simplification is a strategy that we use not only in translating complex texts but also in our daily lives. For example, when talking to a colleague about work-related issues, we do not feel the need to degrade our language as we share the same jargon. However, when talking to our parents/friends or anyone outside the field about work or research-related issues, we automatically try to use simpler words to become more understandable. In this regard, this study once again proves how lexical simplification is nested in our lives, textbooks, curriculums, and daily conversations while we are not even aware of it.

Conclusion

This study seeks to determine how the simplification strategy was used in the abstracts of Masters Theses in Turkish and their English translation. For the study, the abstracts of MA theses translated from Turkish to English in the field of medicine were selected. These texts comprise MA theses written by Turkish speakers of English in medicine. The abstracts were chosen randomly from MA theses between 2020-2023. They were available at the Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education. To examine the simplification, it was mainly applied three taxonomies of simplification. The first one is the main taxonomy, the linguistic simplification of Honeyfield, and its sub-categories: lexical and syntactic simplification.

This study found that lexical simplification was used more than syntactic simplification in medical texts. The most prominent finding to emerge from this study is that in the translation of medical texts examined for this research, “transfer” was preferred. The current data highlights the importance of simplification strategies, especially for fields such as medicine, which has specific terminology. Also, this paper contributes to the area of translation and further studies as there is not much research on the simplification strategies in medical texts.

In conclusion, simplification strategies in medical texts were examined in the present study. The results show that simplification strategies are commonly used in medical texts, making it easier to understand them. However, the scope of this study was limited to linguistic simplification, and the major limitation of this study was being able to examine only 40 medical texts written between 2020-2023. Thus, further studies that look at more comprehensive data are needed.

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Genişletilmiş Türkçe Özet

Tıbbi çeviri, yabancılara veya azınlıklara sağlık hizmeti sunulmasında kritik bir faktör olabilmektedir. Bu amaçla uygulanan birçok çeviri metot ve tekniği bulunmaktadır. Fakat hangi durumlarda ne gibi metot ve tekniklerin kullanıldığıyla ilgili literatürde pek az çalışma mevcuttur. Tıbbi metinlerin çevirisini doğru bir şekilde sürdürmek kritik bir uygulamadır, bunu sağlamak için çevirmenler bazı çeviri stratejilerinden yararlanırlar. Bu stratejilerden en yaygın olanlarından biri Baker tarafından önerilen “sadeleştirme” stratejisidir. Tıbbi tercümelere sadeleştirme, karmaşık tıbbi terminolojiyi anlaşılır bir dille ifade etme sürecine verilen isimdir. Sadeleştirme, genel olarak hastalar ya da halk için anlaşılabilir ve erişilebilir bir dil kullanmayı içerir. Tıbbi terimlerle dolu karmaşık metinler, geniş bir kitle tarafından anlaşılabilir ve yalnızca belli bir grup ile sınırlı kalabilir. Bu durum, hastaların sağlık durumları, tedavi seçenekleri ve tedavi öncesinde ve sonrasında alınabilecek önlemler hakkında bilgi edinmelerini zorlaştırabilir. Sadeleştirilmiş tıbbi metinler sayesinde bilgilere erişim kolaylaşmaktadır. Bu bakımdan sadeleştirme stratejilerini incelemek önem arz etmektedir. Baker sadeleştirme stratejisini çeviri evrensellerinden bahsederken net olarak açıklamaktadır. Çeviri evrenselleri kavramı, çeviribilim alanında önemli bir ilgi alanıdır. Bu bağlamda, Baker bir çeviride sadeleştirme yaparken kullanılacak dört farklı prensipten bahsetmiştir bunlar; benzerlik evrenseli, işlevsellik evrenseli, kültürel evrensel ve metinsel evrenseldir. Baker’a göre, çeviride bu prensiplerin tamamı sadeleştirme sürecinde bir denge içinde kullanılmalı, ve birbirine çatışmamalıdır. Bu bağlamda çalışmanın amacı, tıp alanındaki Türkçe yüksek lisans tezlerinin özetlerinde ve bunların İngilizce tercümelerinde sadeleştirme stratejisinin nasıl korunduğunun açıklanmasıdır. Araştırmanın özünü iki araştırma sorusu oluşturmaktadır: “Türkçeden İngilizceye çevrilen tıp metinlerinin özetlerinde sözcük sadeleştirme stratejilerinin dağılımı nasıldır?”, “Türkçeden İngilizceye çevrilen tıp metinlerinin özetlerinde sözdizimsel sadeleştirme stratejilerinin dağılımı nasıldır?”. Sadeleştirmeyi incelemek için, temel olarak üç basitleştirme taksonomisi uygulanmıştır. Ana taksonomi Honeyfield’in dilbilimsel basitleştirmesidir, diğer taksonomiler Blum-Kulka ve Levenston’ın sözcüksel basitleştirmesi ve Mountford’un sözdizimsel basitleştirmesidir. Verilerin geçerliliğini sağlamak için 2020 ve 2023 yılları arasında her yıl için 10 yüksek lisans tezi seçilmiştir bununla birlikte tıp alanındaki yüksek lisans tezlerinin özetleri arasından 40 özet incelenmiştir. Bu çalışmada Türkçeden İngilizceye çevrilen tıp metinlerinde sadeleştirme stratejilerinin incelenmesi amaçlandığından veriler iki kategoriye ayrılmıştır: Türkçe yazılan özetler ve İngilizceye çevrilen özetler. Bu yazıdaki veri kodlamaları yayın yılı ve dilin ilk harfi olacak şekilde düzenlenmiş ve tematik analiz kullanılmıştır. Örnek vermek gerekirse 2020-T-1, 2020 yılında yazılan ilk Türkçe özet, 2020-E-1 ise aynı özetin İngilizceye tercüme edilmiş versiyonuna karşılık gelir. Elde edilen bulgulara göre tıp metinlerinde sözdizimsel sadeleştirmeden çok sözcüksel sadeleştirme kullanılmaktadır. Tercümanların sözdizimsel sadeleştirmeden ziyade sözcüksel sadeleştirmeyi tercih etmelerinin olası sebepleri, bu çalışmanın tartışma kısmında ilgili literatürden örnekler verilerek açıklanmaya çalışılmıştır. Sonuçlar, sadeleştirme stratejilerinin tıp metinlerinde yaygın olarak kullanıldığını ve tıp metinlerinin anlaşılmasını kolaylaştırdığını göstermektedir. Ancak bu çalışmanın kapsamı dilsel sadeleştirme ile sınırlı tutulmuştur ve en büyük sınırlılık 2020-2023 yılları arasında yazılan sadece 40 tıbbi metni incelenemesi olmuştur. Bu nedenle daha kapsamlı verileri inceleyen, daha fazla çalışmaya ihtiyaç vardır. Bu çalışmanın tıp alanında yapılan tercüme çalışmalarına bir farkındalık kazandırarak bundan sonra kullanılacak tıbbi tercüme teknikleri hakkında tercümanlara ve tüm tıp çalışanlarına bir içgörü kazandırması beklenmektedir.